

Built by AI, Powered by AI

Lessons from building two applications on Open Research Information

Nick Veenstra (UMCG Research Bureau, RUG Library)

About me

- Data engineer on the shared UMCG/RUG research information data warehouse
- AI Engineer / LLM Ops for AI servers at UB/RUG and Research Bureau (UMCG)
- Pure handyman
- AI driven robotics enthusiast

Building with AI in the research information domain

- After completing our data warehouse with a lot of “chat” help (2022-2025, no coding agents yet), started working on two new AI driven projects:
 - Pure middleware solution that auto feeds Scopus, OpenAlex, ROR, HR data to Pure to leverage Pure team workload (**VAL**idation **EN**richment and **RE**search **IN**tegration **EN**gine, **VALERIE**). Cleaned up 118K external collaborations.
 - AI Support application for the UMCG Grant office (**AI-GO**); determines researcher and organizational expertise, gathers and classifies funding opportunities, matches with researchers for newsletters, chatbot and personal advice pages. All using local AI.

VALERIE

VALERIE Validation Enrichment and Research Integration Engine v1.6.0 Overview Publ. Candidates **Ext. Orgs** Staff & Orgs Jobs Settings

External Organizations Cleaned DOI+Author Local ROR Scopus Bridge Embed+Graph **ID Mappings** Pure Sync

Search name or ID... ROR ID: Present Missing Scopus afid: Present Missing Pure UUID: Present Missing 182,790 rows

Export CSV Queue for Pure update (182,790) Reset Pure queues Reset all

Total rows 182,790 Unique Pure 182,293 Unique ROR 17,054 Unique Scopus 26,333 Pairs 112,077 Triplets 17,611

NAME	PURE UUID	ROR ID	SCOPUS AFID	SOURCE
&Talent Netherlands	662b3827-d1cd-47a8-8dab-e3236b459783	-	-	Pure
&samhoud	a317b7b1-f4ff-42a8-87e6-d750e1aa2b44	-	-	Pure
OTLife Institute	4a8625de-45c1-48f5-93d1-6d480be3efa6	-	-	Pure
OTLife Institute Shenzhen, China	4ba9b8e1-2444-4645-8ef5-43f194ed6db6	-	131344881	Pure

- 0Department of Biomedical Sciences, College of Medicine, University of Malawi
Blantyre, Malawi
University of Malawi
Zomba, Malawi
- 0Strahlentherapiepraxis Distler
Germany
- 1000shapes GmbH
Berlin, Germany
- 10Amsterdam UMC location University of Amsterdam, Hematology
Amsterdam, Netherlands
Amsterdam UMC Location University of Amsterdam
Amsterdam, The Netherlands
- 10Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Ekerliek Hospital
Helmond, Netherlands
Ekerliek Ziekenhuis
Helmond, The Netherlands

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Run HR sync
Fetch latest CSVs from SFTP, build XML, upload to the Pure pull-container. Runs in the background — watch the Jobs page for progress. Run → test Run → prod

Organisations **4,184** Persons **16,567** Users **16,567**

IMPORT HISTORY

Date	Status	Upload	Orgs	Persons	Users
05/06/2026 00:00	✓ accepted	✓ prod	4,184	16,567	16,567
04/06/2026 23:00	✓ accepted	✓ test	4,184	16,567	16,567
04/06/2026 10:51	✓ accepted	✓ prod	4,184	16,567	16,567
04/06/2026 10:00	✓ accepted	✓ test	4,184	16,567	16,567
04/06/2026 10:00	✓ accepted	✓ test	4,184	16,567	16,567

STAFF RELATIONS BY EMPLOYMENT TYPE

VALERIE Validation Enrichment and Research Integration Engine v1.6.0 Overview **Publ. Candidates** Ext. Orgs Staff & Orgs Jobs Settings

Publication Candidates Search title or author... From - To All Candidate Approved Rejected Scopus OpenAlex 21,128 records

TITLE	FIRST AUTHOR	YEAR	TYPE	DOI	SOURCES	STATUS
Rapid DNA cleavage by the LINE-1 endonuclease proximal to DNA ends and at mismatches	Bryant D. Miller	2026	Journal	10.1016/j.jbc.2025.11...	Scopus	candidate
Impact of an AI-powered hospital admission prediction dashboard to guide medication reconciliation in the emergenc...	J. Maathuis	2026	Journal	10.1007/s11096-025-02...	Scopus OpenAlex	candidate
Treatment of anterior saphenous vein incompetence with mechanochemical endovenous ablation	M.E. Witte	2026	Journal	10.1177/026835525141...	Scopus OpenAlex	candidate
Mental hospitalisation and its impact on mortality	Govert E. Bijva...	2026	Journal	10.1016/j.ehb.2025.10...	Scopus	candidate
Preface	Michael H.F. Wi...	2026	Book Series	eId:105921008100	Scopus	candidate
Comparison of the Effectiveness of Fascia Iliaca Compartment Block for Preoperative Pain Relief in Patients With Intracapsula...	Elke Stenvers	2026	Journal	10.1177/2151459325141...	Scopus OpenAlex	candidate
Metaphor in the Mental Lexicon: Investigating Different Types of Polysemy via Eye-Tracking and Behavioral Experiments	Valentina Apres...	2026	Journal	10.1008/10926488.2025...	Scopus OpenAlex	candidate
Monolayer nanocrystalline graphene synthesized from pyrolyzing a Langmuir monolayer of a polyaromatic hydrocarbon	Xue Liu	2026	Journal	10.1126/sciadv.adv18956	Scopus OpenAlex	candidate
Quantifying the fatal and non-fatal burden of disease associated with child growth failure, 2000–2023: a systematic...	Christopher E. ...	2026	Journal	10.1016/s2352-4642(25...	Scopus	candidate
COGNITION, INTERACTION, AND DEVELOPMENT, WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO EDUCATION OF THE HANDICAPPED...	Ton van der Ge...	2026	Book	10.4324/9781083714415...	Scopus	candidate

Showing 1–25 of 21,128 < 1/846 >

AI-GO

Personal

RESEARCHER
Currently — search to change...

576
PUBLICATIONS
159 classified

Biomaterialen algemeen

TOP RESEARCH ACTIVITIES
Development of treatments and therapeuti... 69 pubs | Evaluation of treatments and therapeutic in... 11 pubs | Detection screening and diagnosis 10 pubs

TOP HEALTH CATEGORIES
Cancer and neoplasms 64 pubs | Skin 21 pubs | Neurological 14 pubs

UMCG: AI-GO AI RESEARCH ASSISTANT **Research Assistant**
Ask questions about UMCG publications and research expertise + New chat

Overview
Personal
Expertise
Publications
Research Assistant
Funding Opportunities
Jobs
Settings

Ask anything about UMCG research
Click a question to try it, or type your own below.

Who are our top researchers in cardiovascular disease?
What publications do we have on diabetes and obesity?
Which groups work on machine learning in medical imaging?
Summarise UMCG expertise on rare genetic disorders.

Powered by gemma4-e4b via Ollama - responses grounded in UMCG publication corpus

Personal overview

The focus on advanced biomaterials, immunotherapy, and cancer biology aligns well with several current funding opportunities. For work on treatment strategies, consider [Accelerating Product Excellence in Innovation and for Clinical Adoption \(APEX\)](#) (U24 Clinical Trial Not Allowed) products, with a deadline of 2026-07-10 and a budget of €6,000,000. Given your expertise in developing novel cancer interventions, the [Interventions \(TTNC\): R01 Clinical Trial Not Allowed](#) is highly relevant, encouraging pre-clinical research for nanotechnology-based cancer complexities of the brain, particularly circuit-specific processes, could be supported by the [BRAIN Initiative: Development and Validation of Specific Processes in the Brain \(R01 Clinical Trial Not Allowed\)](#), which has a deadline of 2027-02-08. If your work involves analyzing the [Integrating Biospecimen Science Approaches into Clinical Assay Development \(U01 Clinical Trial Not Allowed\)](#) offers support for mitigation of a deadline of 2027-09-10. For foundational work in neuroscience, the [NIH Blueprint Initiative: Tools for Germline Gene Editing in the Nervous System](#) offers support for

Dashboard Opportunities Matches Newsletter

DEADLINES: Today - 7 This week - 31 This month - 22

SOURCES

Alzheimer Nederland 8 open 2 matches for 609 candidates	EIT Health 3 open 1 matches for 40 candidates	Gates Grand Challenges 3 open 3 matches for 1,231 candidates
Health Holland 4 open - 1 forthcoming 1 matches for 42 candidates	Horizon Europe 848 open - 472 forthcoming 21 matches for 566 candidates	KWF 9 open - 3 forthcoming 2 matches for 423 candidates
NIH 531 open - 279 forthcoming 373 matches for 2,649 candidates	NWO 45 open 3 matches for 137 candidates	RVO 215 open - 11 forthcoming 3 matches for 51 candidates
ZonMw 47 open - 3 forthcoming 17 matches for 345 candidates		

Expertise

Dashboard Organizations Researchers

YEAR RANGE: From - To
ORG TYPE: Research programme 1
ORGANISATION: BRAIN 1
Active only Clear filters

Publications over time

Expertise heatmap
Researchers per RA x HC — click a cell to explore

AI coded, AI based

- Planned time frame for both products: 6 months. Claude Code was used to build both applications. Initial working AI-GO product: 1.5 weeks.
- Claude does not run the software
- AI-GO software uses local models on an NVIDIA DGX Spark. All data is stored and inferenced locally.
- Claude knows my work, Pure, Scopus, OpenAlex file structures and datamodel, how to build a RAG setup, write project plans (superpowers skills), extensive documentation, detailed P&S reports.
- AI enables switching to open vocabularies with rapid classification

Now what?

- Nobody will read all that documentation
- Bombarding P&S officials with extremely detailed reports
- The AI race: should I share AI-GO code with you?
- Not allowed to share 118.000 Scopus <> ROR org id fixes
- Claude discussion at the UMCG : security vs productivity
- Think before you buy rent publisher X's next AI tool for 20K per year (That's 200 months of Claude Max subscriptions, investment for your staff)
- How do we collaborate? Multi developer, multi AI agent coding
- "Have your agent contact my agent"

Future vision Andrej Karpathy (Anthropic)

- Agentic coding: software 3.0 (programming via prompting)
- Vibe coding raises the floor for everyone; agentic engineering preserves the professional quality bar (security, reliability) while going faster
- ‘We can now outsource our thinking but not (yet) our understanding, and that understanding remains the key bottleneck and the thing most worth learning deeply’

```
• Update Todos
  ✓ Task 1-Add /api/cordis/similar-to-call-endpoint
  ✓ Task 2-Extend /api/cordis/projects-with-ids[]-param
  ✓ Task 3-Add Similar-projects-pill-on-FundingList
  ✓ Task 4-ProjectsTab-URL-state+banner
  ✓ Task 5-Version-bump+DESIGN.md
  * Task 6: Hand off to user

• Increment C is complete and committed. Bumped to backend 0.97.24 / frontend 0.47.19.
  What shipped:
  • GET /api/cordis/similar-to-call?call_id=&limit= — cross-collection Qdrant search ( funding_ec_embeddings → cordis_projects_embeddings , score floor 0.40)
  • /api/cordis/projects accepts repeatable ids[] ; preserves input order when set
  • "Similar projects" pill on Horizon Europe rows in FundingList (uses e.stopPropagation() )
  • ProjectsTab reads ids / similar_call from URL, shows a teal banner with a Clear similarity filter button, and Clear filters drops them too

Backend Python + frontend changed, so run ./deploy.sh --build .
Click-through tests to verify:

1. EU Calls tab — every Horizon Europe row has a teal "Similar projects" pill; NWO/NIH/charity rows don't.
2. Click a pill on a known asthma-related call → land on Projects tab, banner shows "Showing projects similar to selected call (N)", top row should be the most asthma-related CORDIS project.
3. Toggle an RA chip on top of the similarity view → count drops (intersection); remaining rows still in similarity order.
4. "Clear similarity filter" → banner gone, full project list returns, HRCS chips remain.
5. "Clear filters" (when only similarity is active) → both ids and similar_call drop from URL.
6. Direct URL /european?tab=projects&ids=<csv> → deep-link works.
7. Pill on a call with no embedding → endpoint returns empty list → Projects tab shows empty state + banner; Clear filter restores.
```

Takeaways

- At some point we will move from this ‘age of personalized software’ (built by you for mostly/only you) to agentic AI as the interface
- AI will show data insights without having to use Power BI or any pre- or custom built software. A PC will basically be hardware + LLM’s (in an open, local scenario). LLM’s will become the OS.
- Only qualitative and accessible data will matter: clean your data, use open identifiers to link, implement MCP servers for AI agents
- P&S pushback: we work mostly with open data: ideal for AI experiments
- Own your *data*. The *software* you’re thinking about buying now will be useless within 5 years

Questions?